

AN OVERVIEW OF GROWTH TRENDS OF SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN KARNATAKA

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the development of the school education system in Karnataka. India is the largest and most complex education system in the world. The growth of this system runs parallel to the future of our country, as reflected in the quality of the current education system. A school must stimulate curiosity in young, impressionable minds and equip them with the tools to become better human beings. This study examines the school education system, including key facts and figures about the sector, the structure of schooling at each level, language policy and practice in education, and teacher education.

In Karnataka, the education sector is making substantial progress. According to the 2001 Census, the literacy rate was 66.64%, which increased to 75.60% as per the 2011 Census. Currently, Karnataka ranks ninth in the country in terms of literacy rate. The state's literacy growth plans indicate strong prospects for a sustainable future. Karnataka enjoys a leading position economically, largely due to the extensive knowledge base of its society. This intellectual capital can significantly contribute to achievements and reforms in the education sector, particularly in school education. With over 77,000 schools, 1.03 crore students, and 3 lakh teachers, the Department of Primary and Secondary Education has implemented various

initiatives to enhance the quality of education in the state. Performance in school education plays a critical role in achieving sustainable development. High-quality education is an essential tool for building a more sustainable world—both for India as a whole and for Karnataka in particular. This research paper focuses on recent developments in school education, including literacy rates, access to education, and student enrolment.

Keywords: School Education System, Literacy Rate, Sustainable Growth of Schools, Access, and Enrolments.

Introduction

The Indian school education system is one of the largest and most significant in the world, catering to over 260 million young individuals each year. At both the national and state levels, various initiatives have been undertaken to improve access to quality education, particularly for those who are economically and socially disadvantaged. Amid growing competition from private schools, efforts within the government sector have been directed towards providing parents and children with access to quality education that enhances life opportunities. Karnataka, with its strong knowledge base, continues to be one of India's leading economies. This intellectual foundation contributes positively to significant achievements and reforms in the education sector. The literacy rate in Karnataka increased from 66.64% in 2001 to 75.60% in 2011, marking a notable improvement. While the urban male literacy rate has surpassed 90%, the rural female literacy rate remains below 60%. Karnataka ranked ninth among 16 major states in terms of literacy in both 2001 and 2011, maintaining its position over the decade.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the performance and status of the school education system in India and Karnataka.
2. To examine the role and characteristics of the school education system in the education sector.
3. To analyse the growth trends of the school education sector in Karnataka.

Research Methodology

This paper is primarily based on secondary data and descriptive analysis. It draws upon several annual reports from the Department of Education, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, Government of Karnataka, the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), and Educational Statistics at a Glance, along with data from the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, the Economic Survey of Karnataka (2019–20), various reputed journals, articles, websites, and other relevant sources. For the analysis, statistical tools such as percentages, averages, Annual Growth Rate (AGR), and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) have been employed.

School Education System in India

The Indian school education system is one of the largest and most significant in the world—second only to China—serving over 260 million young people annually. Since committing to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in 2000, India has made substantial progress toward achieving universal primary education. According to World Bank reports, between 2000 and 2017, elementary school enrolment increased by more than 33 million, rising from 156.6 million in 2000–01 to 189.9 million in 2017–18. Although the extent of achievement

varies across India's 29 states and seven union territories, nearly two-thirds have reported achieving universal primary enrolment. Two landmark initiatives by the Government of India— Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) launched in 2001, and the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act enacted in 2009—have played a vital role in improving access, inclusivity, and quality in education. Additionally, the mean years of schooling for the working-age population rose from 4.19 years in 2000 to 6.4 years in 2017. India remains committed to achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and in recent years, has introduced several large-scale and ambitious programs aimed at further strengthening the education system and meeting these global targets.

Role of School Education System in Sustainable Development

Sustainable development involves integrating social, environmental, and economic concerns to create development pathways that meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. School Education for Sustainable Development (SESD) represents a vision of education that aims to balance human and economic well-being with cultural traditions and the Earth's natural resources. SESD emphasizes learning approaches that facilitate the transition toward sustainability. These include future-oriented education, citizenship education, education for a culture of peace, gender equality, and respect for human rights, health education, population education, environmental conservation, and sustainable consumption. Education for sustainable development is increasingly viewed as a process of learning to make informed decisions that take into account

the long-term future of the economy, environment, and social well-being of all communities. Building the capacity for such futures-oriented thinking is a fundamental role of education.

Importance Features of Education for Sustainable Development

- This is based on the principles and values that underlie sustainable development.
- To deal with the well-being of all three realms of sustainability – environment, society and economy;
- To promote lifelong learning for students in rural and urban areas;
- This is locally relevant and culturally appropriate.
- It is also based on local needs, perceptions, and conditions, but acknowledges that fulfilling local needs often has international effects and consequences;
- To involve formal, non-formal and informal education;
- To accommodate the evolving nature of the concept of sustainability;
- The address's content, taking into account context, global issues and local priorities;
- To build civil capacity for community-based decision making, social tolerance, environmental stewardship, an adaptable workforce and quality of life;
- This is interdisciplinary: no one discipline can claim ESD as its own, but all disciplines can contribute to ESD;

- To use a variety of pedagogical techniques that promotes participatory learning and higher-order thinking skills.

An Overview of School Education in Karnataka

The education sector in Karnataka has shown significant growth in recent years. According to the 2001 Census, the literacy rate stood at 66.64%, which increased to 75.60% by 2011. The state's literacy growth strategies highlight promising prospects for sustainable education development. School education in Karnataka is structured into Lower Primary Schools (Classes I to V), Higher Primary Schools (Classes I to VII/VIII), and High Schools (Classes VIII to X). According to the Department of Education, elementary education was 83.14% of lower primary and 60.86% of higher primary schools achieving substantial coverage. However, the government's involvement in secondary education remains limited, with only 29.59% of high schools managed by the state. Government schools are primarily located in rural areas, whereas private schools are concentrated in urban regions. As of 2020, there were 62,319 elementary schools in Karnataka, comprising 24,316 lower primary and 38,003 higher primary schools.

The Right to Education (RTE) Act was officially notified in Karnataka in 2011, laying down regulations to ensure free and compulsory education for children, further strengthening the foundation of equitable school education in the state.

Over the years, the enrollment has increased marginally in the primary stage. Enrolment during 2018-19 in primary (class I to V) and in upper primary (class VI to VIII) stage is estimated to be 54.82 lakh and 30.50 lakh respectively. The number of SC / ST children in

classes I to VII in the State is 1463084. During 2018-19, the Gross Enrollment Ratio and NER at the lower primary are 104.40 and 95.72, respectively and at the higher primary stage, they are 97.07 and 81.77, respectively. During 2018-19, the dropout rate is LPS and HPS, 1.42 percent and 2.19 percent, respectively. A total number of 281768 teachers of the sanctioned 315557 teachers (89.29%) are working in the LPSs and HPSs under the State Government during 2018-19. In addition, 22055 teachers were sanctioned, and 15931 teachers are working in aided schools at the elementary stage. The average Pupil-Teacher Ratio is 1:26.06 at the elementary stage.

Literacy in Karnataka

A review of growth of literacy during the 2001–2011 decade shows that Karnataka has achieved significant progress. Karnataka's literacy rate in 2011 was 75.60 percent, compared to 66.64 percent in 2001. Karnataka's overall literacy rate, male and female literacy rates are above the national average. Urban male literacy rate in the State has crossed 90 per cent. However, rural female literacy rate in the State is yet to cross 60 per cent as given in Table-1. The literacy rank of the State was nine among 16 major States in 2001 and it has maintained the same position as in 2011.

The overall increase in literacy rate in the State during this decade is 9 percent. Districts like Kalburgi (undivided), Bengaluru Rural, Bagalkot, Raichur, Kolar, Chamarajanagar, Vijayapura and Bidar with a lower literacy rate in 2001 have crossed the State average literacy rate in 2011. This is recognized as literacy development schemes implemented by the Department of Education with a focus on backward districts/ regions of the State. The SSA and

RMSA initiatives resulted in good schooling facilities, attractive incentive schemes to improve learning, quality assurance measures and increased awareness among the community.

Table -1 Percentage Distribution of Literacy Rate in Karnataka 2011

S. No	Category	Rural Area	Urban Area	Overall Karnataka
1	Persons	68.73	85.78	75.36
2	Male	77.61	90.04	82.47
3	Female	59.71	81.36	68.08

Source: 2011 Census

Sustainable Growth of School Education in Karnataka

The School Education System has been divided into several levels viz., pre-primary level, primary level, upper primary, and secondary education, undergraduate and post-graduate education in the state. Karnataka is imparted through Lower Primary Schools (LPS, class I to V), Higher Primary Schools (HPS, class I to VII /VIII) and High Schools (VIII to X) in school education. These schools fall into fewer than three categories based on kind of management and they are - Government schools managed by the Departments of Education, Social Welfare and local self-governments; Government aided schools; and Private unaided schools. During 2018-19, there were 25278 lower primary, 36951 higher primary and 15867 high schools in the State. In the total number of schools, the percentage of Government education department's schools is as high as 83.14 percent in lower primary schools and 60.86 percent in higher primary schools. However, the Education Department's participation is low in secondary education as the Government manages only 29.59 percent of the high schools. Out of 8.78 lakh girls students

enrolled in high schools during 2019-20, 34.62 percent are enrolled in Government High schools and 65.38 percent of them study in aided/unaided/other schools.

□ **Elementary Education in Karnataka**

Article 21 A of the Constitution of India and the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Elementary Education (RTE) Act 2009 developed functioning in 2010. The State Rules under the RTE Act were notified in 2011. These developments have thrown open fresh opportunities for quality schooling for children. There are indicators such as – access, number of schools, enrolments, dropout rates, and infrastructure.

□ **Access of School Education**

In Karnataka, schools have been a significant development in improving access. Karnataka has the policy to start a new primary school within one kilometer in habitations where the population is more than 100 and child population is more than 10. All habitations with a population of 100 and above now have access to a primary school within a distance of one kilometer. HPS are being up-graded to include class 8, wherever there are no High Schools within 3 Kilometers. A total number of 7817 HPS has been upgraded so far.

□ **Status of Schools**

In Karnataka, there were 62229 elementary schools, of which 25278 were LPS and 36951 were HPS during 2018-19, compared to 25801 lower primary schools, and 36206 higher primary schools during 2017-18. The number of LPS decreased by 962 and HPS increased by 1052 between 2018-19 and 2019-20. There were 15,867 high schools in the state during 2018-19 and

16,808 schools during 2019-20. There is an increase of 941 schools during 2019-20. Table-2 shows the growth of school education in Karnataka during the period from 2014-15 to 2019-20.

Table -2 Growth Trends of Schools in Karnataka (2014-15 to 2019-20)

(In Numbers)

Year	Lower Primary	Higher Primary	High Schools	Grand Total	AGR
2014-15	26308	34604	14937	75849	-
2015-16	26118	34795	15140	76053	0.27
2016-17	26696	35498	15773	77967	2.52
2017-18	25801	36206	15666	77673	-0.38
2018-19	25278	36951	15867	78096	0.54
2019-20	24316	38003	16808	79127	1.32
Average	25752.83	36009.50	15698.50	77460.83	
CAGR	-1.49	1.93	2.09	0.82	

Source: Government of Karnataka (2019), Karnataka at a Glance, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Bengaluru.

The above table indicates the average and CAGR for the number of schools and total enrolment of school education in Karnataka during the period from 2014-15 to 2018-19. During 2014-15, a total number of 26308 LPS, which decreased to 24316 in 2019-20. The HPS is 34604 in 2014-15, and it has increased to 38003 in the year 2019-20. The high schools are also increasing trend from 14937 to 16808 during the period between 2014-15 and 2019-20. The overall school education institutions were 75849 in 2014-15, which increased to 79127 in 2019-20. The average for the lower primary is 25752.83, higher primary is 36009.50, high schools are 15698.50 and the total of school education is 77460.83. The CAGR for the growth of school education in the state, which has lower primary schools is -1.49 percent, higher primary is 1.93 percent, higher schools is 2.09 percent and overall schools of CAGR is 0.82 percent during the

period from 2014-15 to 2019-20. The AGR for the school education institutions of 0.27 per cent in 2015-16, and it has changed to 1.32 percent in 2019-20.

Enrolments of School Education

Enrolment in the primary (Class I to V) and upper primary (Class VI to VIII) stages was 54.33 lakh and 31.24 lakh, respectively, during 2019-20. 83.24 percent of children are studying in rural government schools. In the previous years, enrolment has decreased marginally in classes I to V of the primary stage and increased marginally in classes VI to VIII of the higher primary stage. This increase in higher primary education is due to the continued efforts made by the State to ensure the successful completion of schooling at class V, and there is a decreasing retention rate at the upper primary stage.

Table- 3 Status of Total Enrolments in Karnataka 2015-16 to 2019-20

All Types of Schools	(In Lakh)				
	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Boys	52.3	52.96	52.59	53.56	53.88
Girls	48.84	48.78	46.65	49.57	50.05
Total Enrolment (1 to 10)	101.14	101.74	99.24	103.13	103.93

Source: Government of Karnataka (2019) Economic Survey of Karnataka 2019-20, Planning, Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Bengaluru.

Table 3 shows that the total enrolment in classes 1 to 10 standards has marginally increased from 101.14 lakh in 2015-16 to 103.93 lakh in 2019-20 in Karnataka. The enrolment of boys in classes 1 to 10 has increased from 52.3 lakh in 2015-16 to 53.88 lakh in 2019-20. The enrolment of girls in classes 1 to 10 has increased from 48.84 lakh in 2015-16 to 50.05 lakh in 2019-20. Both gender parity and gender equity are nearing unity in the State. Gender Parity in enrolment at primary and upper primary is 0.99 and 1.02 in Government and Aided schools. Ratio of girls to boys (gender parity index) in primary education is the ratio of the number of

female students enrolled at the primary level of education to the number of male students in this level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, sustainable development requires the integration of social, environmental, and economic concerns to create development pathways that meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is a vision of education that seeks to balance human and economic well-being with cultural traditions and respect for the Earth's natural resources. ESD emphasizes learning dimensions that support the transition towards sustainability, including future-oriented education, citizenship education, and education for a culture of peace, gender equality and respect for human rights, health education, population education, environmental conservation, and sustainable consumption. It is increasingly recognized as a process of equipping learners with the ability to make informed decisions that account for the long-term future of the economy, environment, and society. Developing the capacity for such futures-oriented thinking is a critical role of education. Key aspects explored include the structure of the school education system, trends in literacy rates, sustainable growth of educational institutions, access to education, and student enrolment. These findings underscore the importance of aligning educational development with the broader goals of sustainability to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all.

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